

COMPETENCIES OF BACHELOR OF ELEMENTARY EDUCATION STUDENTS IN TOMAS CLAUDIO COLLEGES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 10

Pages: 1152-1156

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2631

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14166072

Manuscript Accepted: 10-21-2024

Competencies of Bachelor of Elementary Education Students in Tomas Claudio Colleges

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Abstract

The study aimed to develop the personal and professional qualities and attributes of Bachelor of Elementary Education students at Tomas Claudio Colleges. The result of the study indicates that students are proficient in facilitation, classroom management, communication and human relations. However, there is room for improvement in maintaining and developing these skills, particularly in facilitation, which has the lowest weighted mean of 3.76. The study proposes a program to help students improve their communication, human relations, and facilitation. The inclusion of training workshops, mentorship sessions, experiential learning, collaborative projects, and communication skill development in all year levels of the elementary education program will significantly impact future teaching performance.

Keywords: *elementary education, skills, competencies, facilitation, human relations, classroom management*

Introduction

Competencies involve behaviors, and attitudes, posing challenges for effective management. These competencies are deeply connected with schools' values and culture, rendering them challenging to quantify or standardize. Despite their significance, competencies lack agility and flexibility in practice, often requiring extensive time investments for full development. Unlike specific skills that can be rapidly acquired, achieving competency necessitates substantial dedication. Moreover, competencies are typically associated with specific organizational roles or functions, hindering their transferability across diverse contexts. (Torres 2022).

Teachers require a diverse set of competencies to effectively manage their classrooms and foster student learning. Teachers are the ones who have made the most contribution to students' knowledge, which is why teachers should have a mastery in the area of Teaching Competence of the Bachelor of Elementary Education Student Teachers (Rudolf et al. 2017). In the field of education, Instructional Management play a vital role in improving the professional attributes of Elementary Educators, In the Study of (Raganas N. and Collado L. 2014). They define Instructional Management such as Classroom Management as an action and strategies that are used to maintain order in the classroom. It concerns how the teacher displays the desired competencies using instructional management that will discover the behavior of the learners and will stay active. Communication and Interpersonal ability are crucial, involving the ability to respond sensitively to others' needs and feelings while demonstrating professionalism and clear communication. Organization and Planning are essential for creating effective lesson plans, anticipating student needs, and differentiating instruction. Facilitation and Engagement help maintain student interest and participation in learning activities. Assessment and Coaching abilities are vital for providing constructive feedback and monitoring student progress. Collaboration and Teamwork are important for working effectively with colleagues and promoting a positive school environment. Caring and Inclusiveness involve creating an inclusive and supportive atmosphere for all students, respecting diversity, and understanding individual needs. Flexibility and Adaptability are crucial for adjusting to changing circumstances and overcoming challenges in the educational environment. (Abbotsford School District - Human Resources 2020).

As the field of education continues to evolve, there is a growing emphasis on the competencies and attributes required for effective teaching in the near future. Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEE) programs serve as the foundation for aspiring educators, providing them with the knowledge and skills necessary to excel in their careers. The researchers are interested in exploring the competencies of BEE students at Tomas Claudio Colleges, particularly focusing on professionalism and the attributes of elementary educators. This research aims to understand the current state of preparedness of BEE students and identify areas for improvement to ensure they are equipped to meet the demands of the evolving educational landscape. The researchers seek the cooperation of college students enrolled in the Bachelor in Elementary Education program within the College of Education and Liberal Arts at Tomas Claudio Colleges. The researchers' aim is to assess their current competencies, enhance their proficiency in these areas of knowledge, evaluate their alignment with the course curriculum, and understand the significance of the competencies for their future roles as elementary educators.

Research Questions

This action research aimed to explore the competencies of students enrolled in the Bachelor in Elementary Education program at Tomas Claudio Colleges, and to help elementary educators to develop their personal and professional qualities and attributes in the future. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of competencies of Elementary Education in Tomas Claudio Colleges with respect?

- 1.1. facilitation;
- 1.2. classroom management;
- 1.3. communication; and
- 1.4. human relation?
2. What program can be developed based on the findings?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employs a quantitative research design to analyze numerical data from Bachelor of Elementary Education students at Tomas Claudio Colleges. The researchers use a purposive sampling technique for the selected respondents, utilizing a survey method.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 57 total population of students enrolled in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Bachelor of Elementary Education.

Instrument

The questionnaire is adopted from the study by Jennifer Ramos and Nadyann Felizia Cateria from the study "Instructional Competencies and Work Performance of Teachers in the Basic Education Department in Tomas Claudio Colleges" to determine the extent and competencies of Elementary Education weighted mean was used concerning in facilitation, classroom management, communication, and human relation.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Table 1. *Computed Weighted Mean on the Competencies of Bachelor in Elementary Education Students in Tomas Claudio Colleges with Respect to Facilitation*

<i>I can...</i>	<i>Facilitation</i>	\bar{Wx}	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
1. interact positively with students.		3.98	Much Competent	1
2. emphasize student-centered learning		3.79	Much Competent	3
3. apply multiple technological approaches in teaching		3.65	Much Competent	4
4. tailor-fit task to be far with the pupils learning style		3.53	Much Competent	5
5. give certain task to all so that everyone in the class has something to do		3.88	Much Competent	2
	Overall Mean	3.76	Much Competent	

As reflected in the table, with respect to facilitation, it obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.76, interpreted as much more competent. First in rank indicates that bachelor in elementary education students is much competent to interact positively with students with a weighted mean of 3.98, while last in rank indicates that bachelor in elementary education students is much competent to give certain tasks to all so that everyone in the class has something to do with a weighted mean of 3.53. All the remaining items in the aspect of facilitation are also much competent.

The findings emphasize Tomas Claudio Colleges' Bachelor of Elementary Education students' strong foundational competency in facilitation. These are crucial as they'll have a direct effect on the way instructional methods work in elementary school environments. The broad level of proficiency across all facilitating dimensions indicates that Tomas Claudio Colleges' educational framework effectively fosters the necessary competencies in students. The result is encouraging for elementary education's future and shows that graduates can create welcoming educational environments which cater to the needs and preferences of a wide range of learners.

This is in relation to the study of Gurgenedze (2018) that teaching advancement programs should focus on preparing pre-service teachers to excel in the classroom and raise educational standards. Developing future educators who can compete globally is a challenge for teacher training facilitators.

Table 2. *Computed Weighted Mean on the Competencies of Bachelor in Elementary Education Students in Tomas Claudio Colleges with Respect to Classroom Management*

<i>I can...</i>	<i>Classroom Management</i>	\bar{Wx}	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
1. maintain an adequate classroom discipline.		4.09	Much Competent	3
2. build positive, trusting relationships with pupils.		4.11	Much Competent	1.5
3. remind pupils of classroom rules and indicate what should be done.		4.11	Much Competent	1.5
4. react confidently and quickly in a situation that requires the management of pupil behavior.		3.96	Much Competent	4
5. provide different reinforcement for adhering to the rules.		3.81	Much Competent	5

Overall Mean 4.01 Much Competent

As reflected in the table, with respect to classroom management, it obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.01, interpreted as much more competent. First and tied in rank indicates that bachelor in elementary education students is much competent to build positive, trusting relationships with pupils and remind pupils of classroom rules and indicate what should be done with the tied weighted mean of 4.11, while last in rank indicates that bachelor in elementary education students is much competent to provide different reinforcement for adhering to the rules with a weighted mean of 3.81. All the remaining items in the aspect of classroom management are also much competent.

The data collected indicate an outstanding level of proficiency of bachelor of elementary students in classroom management abilities. Students consistently show proficiency in a range of classroom management areas, including establishing connections and implementing rules. The findings imply that Tomas Claudio College's educational program successfully gives students the tools required to set up productive educational environments in elementary school settings.

This corresponds to Emmer and Sabornie's (2015) assertions that employing classroom management can improve social behavior, promote academic achievement, and foster a healthy classroom atmosphere. We are all aware that classroom management is one of the things that can help teachers effectively manage varied students. Furthermore, Arin et al. (2016) show that effective classroom management can reduce negative student behaviors by creating a pleasant classroom atmosphere.

Table 3. *Computed Weighted Mean on the Competencies of Bachelor in Elementary Education Students in Tomas Claudio Colleges with Respect to Communication*

<i>Communication</i>		<i>W\bar{x}</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
<i>I can...</i>				
1.	speak articulately.	3.75	Much Competent	5
2.	rephrase my questions and/or give clues and hints on how to answer the questions or problems.	3.86	Much Competent	3
3.	try my best to make up different examples which I know all my pupils can relate with.	3.93	Much Competent	2
4.	try my best to make questions or problems fun to answer.	3.84	Much Competent	4
5.	try my best to formulate questions which are enjoyable for the pupils.	3.96	Much Competent	1
Overall Mean		3.87	Much Competent	

As reflected in the table 3, with respect to communication, it obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.87, interpreted as much more competent. First in rank indicates that bachelor of elementary education students is much competent to try their best to formulate questions that are enjoyable for the learners, with a weighted mean of 3.96, while last in rank indicates that bachelor in elementary education students is much competent to speak articulately, with a weighted mean of 3.75. All the remaining items in the aspect of communication are also much competent.

The findings of communication among Bachelor in Elementary Education students at Tomas Claudio Colleges reveal a significant level of proficiency. The overall weighted mean indicates a high competency level, with students excelling particularly in formulating engaging questions for pupils. This proficiency reflects their ability to create interactive and stimulating learning environments conducive to student engagement and participation.

The study by Cohort Nominate (2016) highlights the importance of effective teaching not only in terms of the teacher's knowledge but also in their method and style of communication. It suggests that teaching is not just about knowledge but also about interpersonal or communication. The research highlights the importance of good communication not only for teachers but also for students.

Table 4. *Computed Weighted Mean on the Competencies of Bachelor in Elementary Education Students in Tomas Claudio Colleges with Respect to Human Relation*

<i>Human Relation</i>		<i>W\bar{x}</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
<i>I can...</i>				
1.	encourage harmonious interaction between groups of pupils by emphasizing the value of different approaches to problems	3.72	Much Competent	4
2.	provide opportunities for role-playing by pupils to increase the depth of their understanding of other people and develop a readiness to participate actively with their classmates.	3.60	Much Competent	5
3.	stay aware of the personal problems pupils are facing in their private lives and accept the responsibility for being an adult role model.	3.82	Much Competent	3
4.	provide an example of willingness to change personal attitudes and accommodate other members of the school family.	3.93	Much Competent	1
5.	maintain good rapport with the community and uphold a good image for school community relations.	3.84	Much Competent	2
Overall Mean		3.80	Much Competent	

As reflected in the table, with respect to human relation, it obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.80, interpreted as much more

competent. First in rank indicates that bachelor of elementary education students is much competent to provide an example of willingness to change personal attitudes and accommodate other members of the school family, with a weighted mean of 3.93, while last in rank indicates that bachelor of elementary education students is much competent to provide opportunities for role-playing by pupils to increase the depth of their understanding of other people and develop a readiness to participate actively with their classmates, with a weighted mean of 3.60. All the remaining items in the aspect of human relation are also much competent.

The findings of human relations among Bachelor of Elementary Education students at Tomas Claudio Colleges reveal an outstanding level of proficiency. With an overall weighted mean indicating a significant competency level, students exhibit strong capabilities across various dimensions of human relations. Particularly important are their ability in demonstrating a willingness to adapt personal attitudes and accommodate others, reflecting their ability to foster positive interactions within the school community.

This is in connection with the study of States et al. (2018) that positive teacher-student connections are crucial for enhancing student receptivity to instruction. Teachers should foster a positive classroom environment, treat students respectfully, and set high expectations.

Table 5. *Composite Table on the Competencies of Bachelor in Elementary Education Students in Tomas Claudio Colleges*

<i>Aspect</i>	<i>$W\bar{x}$</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
Facilitation	3.76	Much Competent	4
Classroom Management	4.01	Much Competent	1
Communication	3.87	Much Competent	2
Human Relation	3.80	Much Competent	3
Composite Mean	3.86	Much Competent	

As reflected in the composite table, with respect to facilitating, classroom management, communication, and human relation, with an overall composite mean of 3.86, it is interpreted as much competent. First in rank indicates that bachelor of elementary education students is much competent to classroom management with a weighted mean of 4.01, while last in rank indicates that bachelor of elementary education students is much competent to facilitating, with a weighted mean of 3.76. All the remaining aspects, such as communication and human relation, are found to be much competent.

The combined summary of human relations, communication, facilitation, and classroom management among Tomas Claudio Colleges Bachelor of Elementary Education students reveals a remarkable level of proficiency. Students demonstrate excellent abilities in a variety of areas. Particularly impressive is their competence in classroom management, indicating an outstanding ability to sustain discipline and develop ideal learning environments.

In relation to the study of Daniels (2022), it is emphasized that it is necessary to impart sustainability-related pedagogical knowledge and competences to educators and future teachers. Furthermore, in order to improve sustainable development, higher education institutions must adopt a comprehensive approach that incorporates sustainability ideas, knowledge, and practices into all academic activities.

Proposed Innovation, Intervention, And Strategy

The proposed intervention aims to develop the facilitation and holistic development of a Bachelor of Elementary Education in Tomas Claudio Colleges, the program entitled The Facilitation and Holistic Development Program aims to quip Bachelor of Elementary Education Students with a set of competencies, emphasizes facilitation techniques, effective communication, and fostering positive human relation, Thereby enabling them to create engaging and impactful learning experiences for their future students. This program contains Components.

1. Integrated training workshops and Experiential Learning Modules:

Tailored workshops will cover active learning techniques, group dynamics, effective communication strategies, and fostering positive human relations within educational settings.

Experiential learning modules will be seamlessly integrated into the curriculum, allowing students to apply learned concepts in real-world teaching scenarios, fostering practical experience in facilitation, communication, and interpersonal skills.

2. Collaborative Projects and Communication Skill-Building.

Collaborative projects and group activities will promote teamwork, creativity, and the development of effective communication.

Students will engage in activities focused on active listening, conflict resolution, empathy, and cultural competence, essential for building positive human relations in diverse educational settings.

The facilitation and Holistic Development Program will unfold over a semester long or academic year-long program that includes workshops, mentorship sessions, hands-on modules, reflective exercises, and collaborative projects. Faculty members and experienced educators will collaborate to deliver programs content and membership. this program will continuous evaluation and feedback

mechanisms will ensure the program's effectiveness and facilitate ongoing improvements.

Conclusions

The findings of the study showed that Tomas Claudio Colleges' Bachelor of Elementary Education students' strong foundational competency in facilitation. These are crucial as they'll have a direct effect on the way instructional methods work in elementary school environments. Likewise, the school highlights the importance of continuous professional development for teachers to develop fundamental abilities in elementary education, thereby enhancing academic achievement. Also, their lower speaking articulate ranking suggests the need for further development. Institutions should prioritize training and practical experiences to improve communication. Furthermore, prioritizing specialized interventions and hands-on learning opportunities can strengthen learners' abilities, promote commitment, and foster understanding. This will prepare future educators for positive relationships and holistic growth.

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